

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18865537

Application Of Accounting Information For Improved Financial Management Of Mass Transit Companies In North-Central Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The desire to improve the operational efficiency of the bus mass transit (BMT) companies in North Central Nigeria informed this study. The study was therefore, undertaken to determine the application of accounting information for improved financial management of the BMT companies in the area. Specifically, the study addressed how these companies apply accounting information in two key areas of their financial management, namely; funds sourcing and capital structure decisions. A descriptive survey designed study, the population comprised 36 (20 public-owned and 16 private-owned) bus mass transit companies in the three states covered by the study, viz; Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States, Nigeria. Also, a total of 72 managers made up of 36 General Managers (GM) and 36 Finance Managers (FM) were involved in the study. No sample was drawn as the entire population of bus mass transit companies and their managers in the three states were surveyed. A Likert-like 5-point scale questionnaire comprising 27 items was used to collect data. Research questions were answered by the use of mean (\bar{x}) with standard deviation while t-test at 0.05 level of significance was used to test the null hypothesis using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) analysis. It was found that the BMT managers in the area do not apply accounting information for improved funds sourcing and capital structure decisions. Furthermore, it was found that significant mean differences occurred between the ratings of public and private-owned BMT managers on the extent of application of accounting information for improved capital structure decisions. The difference was found to be in favour of the private-owned BMT managers who applied accounting information in capital structure decisions more than their counterparts in public-owned BMT companies. It was therefore, recommended among other measures that the top management of these companies in the area, in this case, the Board of Directors (BOD) should strictly enforce the use of accounting information in the funds sourcing and capital structure decisions of these companies. This, they can do by ensuring that all accounting information relevant to funds sourcing and capital structure decisions are properly accumulated and timely disseminated to persons that make these decisions for and on behalf of the BMT companies especially the General Managers and Finance Managers.

Keywords: Accounting Information, Financial Management, Funds Sourcing, Capital Structure, & Bus Mass Transit

INTRODUCTION

Transportation as a means of moving people, goods and services from one place to another, is a prime mover of a nation's economy. Even the recent advances in the field of electronic communication and the internet have not undermined the crucial role of transportation to a nation's economic development. This

explains why Agarwal (2002) asserted that a well-planned, adequately maintained, efficiently managed and properly operated transport system is a pre-requisite to all sectors of national development. Mass or public transportation is an important component of transportation the world over.

The mass transit system is a means of moving large number of passengers from one place to another in a single vehicle. It refers to public shared transportation in which the passengers do not travel in their vehicles. The Federal Urban Mass Transit Agency (FUMTA, 1990) identified three categories of mass transit systems in Nigeria, namely; the rail mass transit, the ferry mass transit and the bus mass transit. This study is, however, focused on the bus mass transit which is the dominant mode mass passenger transportation in Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States.

The bus mass transit (BMT) is a system of moving commuters from one destination to another by means of buses of varying sizes- mini buses, medium-sized buses and big buses or coaches. In other words, the BMT is a transport system that comprises motor-buses that convey fare-paying passengers from various origin-locations to various destination-locations. The BMT constitute the major mode of intra-city, inter-state and semi-urban transportation. In fact, Olujide and Adeoti (2009) reported that the BMT system meets 85% of the commuting needs of Nigerians. Public preference for this mode of transportation in Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States could be attributed to the recent hike in the cost of transportation occasioned by the removal of fuel subsidy by the Federal Government of Nigeria. Another reason could be the less government attention in developing other modes of mass transportation like the rail, ferry and even air mass transits in the country. Again, the fact that BMT offers better conveniences like easy access and flexibility of route selection makes it the number one choice of commuters in the area of study.

In order to provide efficient and reliable BMT services to the people, most operators including public-owned BMT outfits have been registered as limited liability companies in Nigeria. Thus, there are two forms of BMT companies operating in the area of study, namely; publicly-owned BMTs (those owned by state or local/municipal councils) and privately-owned BMTs (those owned by individuals and organizations). However, important as these BMT companies are to the economic well-being of the people of North Central Nigeria, operational efficiency challenges are fast crippling these companies in the area in recent times.

The above scenario is evident by the frequent break down of these buses on the high way thereby causing a lot of inconveniences to passengers, the drastic reduction in the fleet of buses available to these companies, and the folding up of most of them in the area of study. Infact, Tunji (2007) observed that the provision of urban public transport services in Nigeria are fast declining due to several factors relating to the present state of the national economy. Simultaneously, public transport demand is accelerating at a very fast rate for similar economic reasons. This paradox, according to the author, may lead to urban and even national mobility crises unless urgent remedial actions are taken. One noticeable intervention needed to address the looming public transportation crises in the North Central States of Nigeria is in the area of efficient financial management of the BMT companies.

Nwude (2003) defined financial management as the process of planning, acquiring and using funds in an enterprise in order to realize its set goals with minimum discomfort and maximum benefit to the enterprise and its owners. The focus of financial management, according to Breadley, Myers and Marcus (2009), is how individuals, organizations, government and companies raise funds/finance and how they apply it to achieve their set objectives. Financial management, as used in this study, are in the areas of funds sourcing and capital structure decisions of the BMT companies in the area of the study.

Funds sourcing is the conscious efforts by managers to raise funds to finance the operations of their companies. Pandey (2003) viewed financing decision as so crucial to an enterprise that whenever a firm makes an investment decision, it must at the same time make the financing decision also. For example, if a BMT company decides to acquire additional buses to boost its operations, it must as well decide on ways of financing such acquisition. Funds sourcing, as used in the context of this study refers to long term sources of financing the BMT companies.

MacMenamin (2005) viewed that there are basically two sources of long term financing, namely; equity funds and debt funds. Equity funds are generated from ordinary shareholders (owners of the company)

who receive dividends as return on their investment in the company. Debt funds, on the other hand, are fixed interest-bearing funds supplied by lenders. These include bonds, debentures, preference shares, long term loans, hire purchase financing, leasing, etc. Since companies in general (including the BMT companies) make use of equity funds as well as debt funds in their financing arrangement, managers of these companies must make capital structure decisions as well.

Capital structure decision, according to Paramasivan and Subramaian (2023), dwells on determining the appropriate mix of equity and debt funds which a firm used to finance its operations in the long term. A firm's capital structure is said to be optimum when the firm selects such combination of debt and equity funds such that the wealth of the firm and that of its shareholders are maximized. At the optimal capital structure level, Gratton (2025) contended that the firm's cost of capital, the weighted average cost of capital (WACC), of the firm is lowest and the firm's market price per share is at its peak. Thus, there is a relationship between funds sourcing and capital structure decisions.

Funds sourcing and capital structure decisions are closely related in the sense that while sourcing for long term finance, a company must ensure appropriate proportion of equity and debt funds and thus, avoid the risk of over-relying on one source of financing which will be detrimental to the enterprise. Over reliance on debt financing, for example, is dangerous because it is capable of plunging a company into financial distress – a situation where a company encounters difficulty in honouring debt obligations to creditors which also include servicing debts owed to long term creditors. Therefore, for the BMT company managers to be able to make worthwhile decisions in funds sourcing and capital structure, Nwude(2003) argued that such managers need to be guided by information drawn from the field of accounting.

Shim, Seigel, Dauber and Qureshi (2015) defined accounting as a service activity that provides quantitative information which can be used for managerial decision-making. Accounting information therefore, represents the output from an accounting system that assists managers in making decisions especially financial decisions. Accounting information comes in the form of financial statements, financial ratios, capital budgets, credit ratings, variances, inventory levels, cost and profitability projections, break-even analysis reports, business plans, etc. It is expected therefore, that managers of BMT companies in the area should use these accounting information to improve their financial management particularly as it relates to funds sourcing and capital structure decisions.

However, the inefficient operations of the BMT companies in the North Central States of Nigeria especially in Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States in recent times point to the inability of managers of these companies to apply accounting information in sourcing for funds. Equally doubtful is the ability of managers of these companies in the area to use accounting information in their capital structure decisions so as to protect these companies from financial distress. Hence the study was designed to determine the extent of application of accounting information for improved financial management of the mass transit companies in the area of the study.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to determine the application of accounting information for improved financial management of mass transit companies in Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States of North Central Nigeria. The specific objectives include:

1. To determine the extent to which the BMT company managers in the area apply accounting information to improve their sourcing for funds; and
2. To determine the extent to which the BMT company managers in the area apply accounting information to improve their capital structure decisions.

Research Questions

1. What extent does the BMT company managers in Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States, apply accounting information to improve their sourcing for funds?
2. What extent does the BMT company managers in the Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States, Nigeria apply accounting information to improve their capital structure decisions?

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey design to illicit the opinions of the BMT company managers on the extent to which they apply accounting information in their financial management decisions in the three states in the North Central Nigeria, namely; Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States. The population of the study consisted of 36 (20 public-owned and 16 private-owned) BMT companies in the area. A total of 72 managers made up of 36 General Managers (GM) and 36 Finance Managers (FM) were involved in the study. The population was accessible and manageable so the entire population was surveyed.

A structured 24-item questionnaire was used to collect data. The instrument was divided into two sections, A and B. While Section A sought for the personal data of the respondents, Section B elicited data to answer the two research questions on a 5-point scale with response options of Very Highly Applied (VHA) – 5points; Highly Applied (HA) – 4points; Averagely Applied (AA) – 3points; Lowly Applied (LA) – 2points; and Not Applied (NA) – 1point. Two experts from the Department of Accounting, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University Makurdi validated the instrument. The reliability testing of the instrument yielded a coefficient of 0.80. Mean (\bar{x}) with standard deviation was used in answering the research questions while t-test at 0.05 level of significance was employed to test the null hypothesis using the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) analysis. For the research questions, any item with a mean rating of equal to or more than 3.50 was accepted as highly applied while any item with a mean rating less than 3.50 was rejected.

RESULTS

Research Question : *To what extent do the BMT company managers in Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States, Nigeria apply accounting information for improved funds sourcing?*

Data collected to answer this research question are presented in Table 1

Table 1. Mean ratings and Standard deviations of BMT company managers’ extent of application of accounting information for sourcing of funds

S/N	Item Statement	N	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
1	The estimated revenue to be generated from the funds that are being sourced	72	3.06	.92	AA
2	The amount of money required for the investment	72	3.25	.95	AA
3	The overhead cost (fixed expenses) of operating the investment	72	2.96	.94	AA
4	The estimated profit from the investment	72	3.14	.98	AA
5	The amount of working capital (cash, spare parts and other consumables) required for the investment to be funded	72	3.56	.80	HA
6	The amount of share capital fully paid by shareholders of the company	72	3.19	1.08	AA
7	The ratio of debts to share capital fully paid by shareholders, that is, debt/equity ratio	72	2.47	.96	LA
8	The company’s total debts (short-term and long term debts)	72	2.46	1.00	LA
9	The name and value of fixed asset(s) to be used as collateral for the amount of loan being sourced for	72	3.56	.92	HA
10	The level of cash available to settle immediate debts (short-term liquidity of the company)	72	3.63	.96	HA
11	Evidence of the company’s ability to pay interest charges on the funds being sourced for out of annual profits	72	3.07	.97	AA
12	The cash flow projections indicating how the	72	2.96	.97	AA

	company will liquidate the loan facility being sourced for				
13	Projected revenue growth rates of the company	72	3.39	1.01	AA
14	Projected profit growth rates of the company	72	3.06	1.07	AA
15	The company's credit ratings by other lending agencies or institutions	72	2.75	1.00	AA
16	Feasibility report of the proposed investment	72	3.53	.87	HA
	Cluster Mean		3.14	.40	AA

The results in Table 1 show that four out of the sixteen items are highly applied in sourcing for funds. In rank order, items 10, 9, 5, and 16 with mean (\bar{x}) scores of 3.63, 3.56, 3.56, and 3.53 respectively were rated highly applied (HA) by the respondents. On the other hand, ten items, namely; 1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 11, 13, 14, and 15 were rated averagely applied (AA). However, items 7 and 8 were rated lowly utilized with mean scores of 2.47 and 2.46 respectively. The cluster mean (\bar{x}) of 3.14 indicates that all the 16 items are averagely applied by the respondents in sourcing for funds. The standard deviation (SD) for the cluster ranges from .80 to 1.07 implying that the respondents' opinions were not far away from the mean.

Research Question Two: *To what extent do the BMT company managers in Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States, Nigeria apply accounting information to improve capital structure decisions?*

In order to answer this research question, 8 items were listed and the respondents were asked to rate on a 5-point scale, the degree at which they apply the items in capital structure decisions. Table 2 shows the summary of their responses.

Table 2. Mean ratings and Standard deviations of BMT company managers' extent of application of accounting information for improved capital structure decisions

S/N	Item Statement	N	\bar{x}	SD	Dec
17	Ascertaining the amount of capital provided by the company's shareholders (equity capital)	72	2.99	1.09	AA
18	Ascertaining the amount of capital to be borrowed from outside institutions (debt capital)	72	2.71	1.05	AA
19	Referring always to the amount of money the company is permitted by law to borrow (debt capacity of the company)	72	2.31	1.18	LA
20	Ascertaining the amount of interest the company is capable to pay on borrowed capital (cost of capital)	72	2.47	1.06	LA
21	Ascertaining the amount of cash available for payment of interest charged on borrowed capital	72	2.72	1.01	AA
22	Ascertaining the value of fixed assets that can be used as collateral for borrowed capital	72	3.57	.62	HA
23	Computing the debt to equity ratio to ascertain the proportion of borrowed capital to company's owned capital	72	2.92	1.03	AA
24	Computing total debt to total capital ratio to determine whether or not to carry additional debt capital	72	2.39	.76	LA
	Cluster Mean	72	2.76	.58	AA

The results in Table 2 reveal that only item 23 with a mean (\bar{x}) value of 3.57 was rated highly applied for capital structure decisions by the respondents. Again, items 17, 18, 21, and 23 with mean values of 2.99,

2.71, 2.72, and 2.92 respectively fall under averagely applied items for this purpose. On the other hand, items 51, 52, and 56 with the obtained mean values of 2.31, 2.47, and 2.39 respectively were rated lowly applied by the respondents. However, the standard deviation (SD) ranges from .62 to 1.18 signifying the spread of the respondents' opinions far away from the mean. The obtained mean for the cluster was 2.76 which imply averagely applied for the items in the cluster in capital structure decisions by the respondents.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

One of the findings of the study revealed that only two sets of accounting information, the amount of working capital required for the investment and the level of cash available to settle immediate debts were rated as applied by the BMT company managers while the rest of the remaining sets of accounting information presented for this purpose were rated as not applied by these managers.

The above finding implies that the BMT company managers in the area of study are not applying accounting information in sourcing for funds. That is, the extent of usage of accounting information in sourcing for funds in these enterprises in the area leaves much to be desired. The few sets of accounting information rated as applied by managers could be the only accounting information that the accounting systems of these companies generates and/or the only accounting information that managers are familiar with. Be that as it may, it then means that the minimum accounting standards prescribed for companies in Nigeria by various bodies such as the Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC), the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), the Nigerian Accounting Standards Board (NASB), etc are not being strictly followed by the BMT company managers in the area. Again, it could be explained that managers who are employed to manage the finances of these companies are not quite knowledgeable in the field of accounting and financial management as a whole or better still, that these managers are not doing their jobs well enough.

However, the findings on the application of accounting information in sourcing for funds in the BMT companies in the area of study are consistent with the views of Abata and Migiroy (2016), that companies in Nigeria are unable to raise loans from banks and other lending institutions largely because of their inability to present bankable proposals (relevant accounting information) to support their applications.

The study further found that the respondents (managers of BMT companies) gave not applied ratings to most of the accounting information that are used for improved capital structure decisions. For instance, accounting information such as the interest the company is capable to pay on borrowed capital – cost of capital; cash available to support interest payment on borrowed capital; the debt/equity ratio of the company; and the debt capacity of the company, all received not applied ratings by the respondents.

The above findings on the use of accounting information in capital structure decisions, again, creates a worrisome situation because Abata and Migiroy (2016) stressed that the capital structure decision of a company must take this vital financial information into account for obvious reason that decisions in this area finance determines the long term solvency of the firm. For instance, the Not Applied rating received from the respondents on the company's debt bearing capacity means that the BMT managers are not aware of the limit the law imposes on their companies' powers to borrow as enshrined in the articles of association of these companies. Hence most of these managers go on borrowing spree to acquire debt capital on terms and conditions most unfavourable to their companies and thus, plunging these companies into financial trouble.

Another interesting revelation of the study was that the public-owned BMT company managers applied accounting information in capital structure decisions more than their private-owned counterparts as shown by the cluster mean values of 2.78 and 2.73 respectively. This implies that the public entities are employing more qualified financial managers than their private counterparts. Better still, it could be explained that there is stricter supervision of the use of accounting information in the public BMT companies than the private BMT companies in the area. Nevertheless, the finding is consistent with the position of Nwude (2003) that capital structure decisions, which determines to a large extent the financial

health of a company both on short-term and long-term basis, should be given maximum attention irrespective of the ownership status if such an entity is to prosper.

CONCLUSION

The paper concluded that the level of application of accounting information for improved financial management in the bus mass transit (BMT) companies in Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States, North Central Nigeria, is generally low. That even in the midst of this low application of accounting information for this purpose amongst the BMT companies in the area, the public-owned-owned companies applied accounting information in financial management more than their private-owned counterparts, especially in capital structure decisions.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. The management of the bus mass transit (BMT) in Benue, Nasarawa and Plateau States headed by their Board of Directors (BOD) should strictly enforce the use of accounting information in their financial management by ensuring that all accounting information relevant to funds sourcing and capital structure decisions are properly accumulated and timely disseminated to the persons or managers responsible for these decisions in these companies. The BOD can hire the services of professional accountants or finance managers in making decisions on these important areas of financial management whenever such need arises in their organizations.
2. BMT managers in the area of study are urged to adopt the use of computer in processing accounting information. This would guarantee more timely and accurate accounting information that would be supplied by the accounting systems of these companies for the purposes of sourcing for and investing funds profitably in these enterprises.
3. The BMT managers are strongly encouraged to apply relevant accounting information such as the debt capacity of the company, cost of capital and debt ratio in their capital structure decisions. This would help them in reducing their companies' cost of mobilizing capital, strengthens the ability of these companies to service debts, and boost shareholders' confidence in the financing arrangements of these companies.
4. BMT companies, especially private-owned, should recruit only qualified and experienced accounting personnel to take charge of their accounting/finance departments. The management of these companies should regularly the knowledge and skills of the accounting personnel so recruited through refresher courses/seminars on the latest technologies of accumulating, processing and use of accounting information in critical areas like sourcing for funds and capital structure decisions. This would help improve the quality of financial decisions in these enterprises generally.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This publication is sponsored by TETFUND. I therefore wish to express my appreciation to the management and authorities of the organization for their sponsorship, which aims to encourage scholarship and educational development in Nigeria.

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